

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE TARGET-BASED DEVELOPMENT OF PATRIOTIC EDUCATION OF FUTURE TEACHERS IN THE CONTEXT OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article examines the conceptual framework for the targeted development of patriotic education among future teachers in higher education institutions of New Uzbekistan. The study emphasizes that patriotic culture should be formed through a systematic pedagogical process that integrates goals, content, methods, resources, and organizational forms. Special attention is given to the role of universities in developing students' civic responsibility, national identity, moral values, and readiness for educational work. The article discusses theoretical approaches to patriotic education, including competency-based, humanistic, personality-oriented, cultural, and activity-based perspectives. It also highlights the importance of classroom instruction, extracurricular activities, discussion clubs, museums, educational projects, and professional practice in strengthening patriotic consciousness. The findings suggest that future teachers should act both as objects and subjects of patriotic education. Developing their patriotic culture is essential for preparing socially responsible, morally mature, and professionally competent educators.*

Keywords: *patriotism of New Uzbekistan, professional competencies, object and subject of the higher education system, future teacher, patriotic culture.*

INTRODUCTION.

The strategy for further development of New Uzbekistan, "Improving the quality and effectiveness of higher education institutions through the implementation of international standards for assessing the quality of education and training"[1], as well as measures to further improve the field of pedagogical education, set such important tasks as "Development of modern teaching staff with a high level of culture, practical professional skills and a deep understanding of educational, methodological and assessment criteria"[2]. This requires clarification of the pedagogical and psychological characteristics of preparing students for educational activities, improvement of organizational and pedagogical conditions, as well as information and methodological support.

Developing spiritual and moral qualities in students at higher education institutions is a multifaceted and complex process. Spiritual and moral education requires the systematic and consistent implementation of comprehensive educational work, which is inextricably linked and mutually beneficial. Only a clear and comprehensive system of educational interventions, a holistic, systemic approach, ensures effective education.[4] Today, reforms in the education system are radically changing the requirements for teachers. In particular, the training of future teachers not only as specialists imparting knowledge, but also as educators, mentors, and public

figures is becoming increasingly important. Therefore, the use of modern approaches in preparing them for educational work is a pressing issue.

The targeted development of patriotism in future teachers is achieved through engaging future teachers in active patriotic activities at the university, taking into account their gradually emerging internal, individual needs.

The driving force behind the development of patriotic culture is the demands that New Uzbekistan places on modern teachers. The development of patriotic culture in future teachers is a specially organized process within the university's patriotic educational environment, with clearly defined goals and objectives for all subjects in the higher education system. By "development," we mean the process and result of the future teacher's interaction with a range of objective, subjective, targeted, and spontaneous external influences. This leads to changes in their system of characteristics and is a manifestation of their qualities under the influence of specially created pedagogical conditions.

DISCUSSION OF RESEARCH ISSUES AND LEVEL IN NEAR ABROAD

More precisely, the concept in education is considered as a combination of various professional, thematic theoretical views on the idea of a "main criterion or project" and the attitudes toward it from various positions. They unite a very general (educational, cultural, social) meaning of the project, its purpose, and the definition of the final result for the specific implementation of the author's concept. The concept of developing a patriotic culture in future teachers is based on the provisions of two concepts, which serve as the criteria for the theoretical justification of a new approach to patriotic education from the perspective of developing a patriotic culture in the individual. These concepts are the education of student youth and the theory of culture, presented by I.M. Ilyinsky, P.I. Babochkin, V.T. Lisovsky, A.I. Machulsky, I.I. Dark, V.E. Davidovich, L.N. Kogan, and A.N. Leontiev [5].

In their concept, I.M. Ilyinsky and P.I. Babochkin demonstrate the unity of cultivating patriotism, ideological orientation, and national sentiment in the individual. The authors see this unity as the key to the future unity of nations. They identified the most important qualities to be cultivated: honor, duty, discipline, loyalty, and selflessness. This concept focuses on the ideological aspect of fostering patriotism and developing a sense of national identity in young people [3].

The second concept of student education by V.T. Lisovsky, A.I. Machulsky, and I.I. Dark, which expresses the approach in the aspect of interest to us, emphasizes the unity of fostering patriotism, a sense of national identity, and an individual's legal consciousness. This position is expressed in the following content: effective methods of development include the targeted development of such qualities in students as love for their homeland, kindness and generosity of nature, high moral standards, determination, a desire for action, perseverance in trials, self-sacrifice, a willingness to survive in difficult times, the ability to defend oneself, justice, and correctness. The authors also emphasize that the position of patriotic activity among university students is, first of all, freed from the manifestation of a sense of responsibility for the effectiveness of the system of which they are subjects.

The development of patriotic activity in future specialists directly depends on the development of personal responsibility for everything that happens at the university, students' active participation in self-governance, a sense of responsibility for their career choices, an understanding of the social significance of their current and future work, and a desire and willingness to act.

In their theory of culture, A.N. Leontyeva, V.E. Davidovich, and L.N. Kogan present culture as a method of personal activity characterized by creative self-realization.

Comparing the essence of these conceptual approaches with our views, we can say that in the latter case, attention should be paid to the student's socio-patriotic activity and their proactive stance.

Today, one of the most pressing problems in our pedagogy is the creation of criteria that reflect a modern understanding of the process of preparing future teachers to educate schoolchildren in the spirit of patriotism and incorporate new works that reveal theoretical and methodological approaches

to the formation of patriots who will create a bright future for the New Uzbekistan.

Based on these, the theoretical foundations of this problem are defined and its practical solution is presented.

The concept represents a systematic and consistent presentation of the foundations, goals, objectives, functions, scientific approaches, principles, and mechanisms for implementing patriotic education in future teachers, as well as the conditions for shaping the education of young people toward big dreams, a new realization of the vision of the future of the New Uzbekistan, and criteria, results, and forecasts for improving this process.

The objectives are achieved through a range of activities conducted both in and outside the classroom.

The objectives of patriotic culture: - regulatory - ensuring the construction of relationships within the "Teacher-Student" system in a multinational society based on tolerance and self-determination; - educational - promoting the intellectual development of future teachers, the assimilation of moral norms, universal and national values, and the development of a conscious and active attitude toward professional activities in the field of patriotic education; - cognitive - equipping future teachers with a system of scientific knowledge necessary to instill in students a patriotism for the New Uzbekistan, ensuring historical continuity, accumulating experience, and developing a system for its transmission from generation to generation.

It should be noted that the cognitive function of patriotic culture is realized in three stages.

The first manifests itself in the context of family upbringing, where initial feelings of love for the Motherland, responsibility, and respect for traditions are formed, and universal human values are assimilated.

The second stage involves the continuity of the socio-historical experience gained at the university. At this stage, the professional and pedagogical qualities necessary for the effective implementation of patriotic teaching activities are developed.

The third stage emphasizes the role of future teachers in transmitting their personal needs to the next generation.

At the university, especially in the pedagogical field, the following scientific approaches are used to develop the patriotic culture of future teachers: competency-based, cognitive-informational, systematic-activity-based, humanistic, subjective, rationalistic, personality-oriented, cultural, hermeneutic, and integrative.

However, achieving concrete results is difficult if the above factors are not taken into account when developing each student's personal competence. Principles for developing personal competence: general pedagogical:

- fundamentalist, • continuity, • humanistic focus;

- the principle of aggregative activity, which implies the unity of activity of all subjects of the university educational field in solving the problems of patriotic development;
- the principle of differentiation of the educational system's content, aimed at selecting historical and cultural values designed to shape the patriotic and active position of pedagogical specialists, university faculty, and future teachers;
- the principle of determining the behavior of future teachers, which implies the design and construction of a patriotically oriented university educational field with the goal of stimulating their patriotic behavior;
- the principle of patriotically dominant activity, which includes the conscious participation of future teachers in patriotically oriented activities.

ANALYSIS RESULTS

The analysis revealed that the process of developing patriotism among future teachers should be considered an independent and holistic pedagogical system that integrates interconnected goals, content, methods, resources, and organizational forms. Such a system is aimed not only at providing knowledge about national values and civic responsibilities but also at fostering patriotic consciousness, emotional attachment to the homeland, social responsibility, and readiness for professional activities related to patriotic education.

From a methodological perspective, the development of patriotism is ensured through the application of various teaching methods. Reproductive methods contribute to the acquisition and reinforcement of knowledge related to national history, culture, and traditions. Analytical methods encourage students to critically examine social and historical events, allowing them to form their own civic positions. Discussion-based methods create opportunities for expressing opinions, defending viewpoints, and developing communicative competence. Problem-solving methods stimulate independent thinking and active participation in addressing social and civic issues, thereby strengthening patriotic beliefs and values.

An important component of the system is the effective use of educational resources. The study showed that discussion clubs, patriotic campaigns, museums, libraries, extracurricular activities, specialized courses, and educational projects create favorable conditions for the development of patriotic culture. In addition, teaching materials, methodological guides, lecture packages, monographs, dictionaries, practical training programs, and curricula serve as valuable resources that support both theoretical understanding and practical application of patriotic values.

The analysis also demonstrated the significance of diverse organizational forms in the development of patriotism. Classroom instruction provides a foundation for acquiring systematic knowledge, while extracurricular activities allow students to apply patriotic values in real-life situations. Individual work promotes self-reflection and personal responsibility, whereas group and paired activities encourage cooperation, mutual support, and collective problem-solving. Furthermore, seminars, binary lectures, independent study, professional internships, and advanced training programs contribute to the formation of professional competencies necessary for implementing patriotic education in future pedagogical practice.

The findings suggest that the effectiveness of patriotic development increases when methods, resources, and organizational forms are integrated into a unified pedagogical system. Such integration enables future teachers to develop not only knowledge and skills but also stable patriotic attitudes, civic responsibility, and professional readiness to educate younger generations in the spirit of patriotism and national values.

CONCLUSION

The results of the study indicate that the formation of patriotic culture among future teachers is a multifaceted pedagogical process that requires a systematic and scientifically grounded approach. Modern higher education institutions should not limit themselves to defining a set of requirements and competencies for future teachers as educators of patriotic values. Rather, they must establish comprehensive mechanisms for assessing and monitoring the development of students' patriotic consciousness, civic responsibility, national identity, moral convictions, and readiness to carry out educational activities aimed at fostering patriotism among younger generations.

Practical experience demonstrates that the effectiveness of patriotic education largely depends on the extent to which future teachers internalize patriotic values and transform them into personal beliefs and professional principles. Therefore, teacher training programs should incorporate not only theoretical knowledge related to patriotism and civic education but also practical activities that encourage students to participate in socially significant projects, community service, cultural initiatives, and educational events aimed at strengthening national values and social responsibility.

In the process of developing patriotic culture, future teachers act simultaneously as both objects and subjects of education. As objects, they acquire knowledge, values, attitudes, and behavioral norms associated with patriotism. As subjects, they actively contribute to the preservation, promotion, and transmission of these values within educational and social environments. By assuming an active subjective position, future teachers demonstrate a conscious patriotic attitude toward socially significant activities, particularly those related to the patriotic upbringing of students and the strengthening of civic engagement.

Furthermore, the development of patriotic views, beliefs, and value orientations among future teachers should be considered one of the key indicators of their professional and personal maturity. A well-developed patriotic culture enhances their ability to educate students in the spirit of respect for national traditions, cultural heritage, social solidarity, and responsibility toward society and the state. It also contributes to the formation of leadership qualities, ethical behavior, and active citizenship.

Thus, the formation of patriotic culture in future teachers should be regarded as an essential component of professional teacher education. Strengthening this process through innovative pedagogical approaches, value-oriented educational technologies, and meaningful practical experiences will contribute to preparing highly qualified specialists who are capable of effectively carrying out patriotic education and fostering socially responsible, nationally conscious, and morally mature younger generations.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 4947 dated February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan"
2. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4623 dated February 27, 2020 "On measures to further improve the field of pedagogical education"
3. Vyrshchikov, A.N. Military-patriotic education: theory and practice [Text] / A.N. Vyrshchikov. -M.: Mysl, 1990. - 150 p.
4. Hegel. Encyclopedia of Philosophical Sciences [Text] / Hegel. / Ed. E.P. Sitkovsky. - Vol. 3. Philosophy of the Spirit. - Moscow: Mysl', 1977. - 471 p.

5. Ippolitova, N.V. Patriotic Education of Student Youth in Modern Conditions [Text] / N.V. Ippolitova // Collection of Scientific Papers. - Khanty-Mansiysk, 2009. - Issue 7. - 232 p.
6. X. Ibraimov, M. Kuronov, J. Fosilov, F. Zaripov; - Tashkent: Gafur Ghulam Publishing and Printing House. 2024. - 220 p.
7. Kogan, L.N. Theory of culture [Text] / L.N. Kogan. - Ekaterinburg, 1993. - 160 s.
8. Ochilov M., Ochilova N. Higher school pedagogy. Textbook. T.: "Alokachi". 2008/
9. Pidkasisty, P.I. Pedagogy [Text] / P.I. Faggot. - M.: Pedagogical Society of Russia, 1998. - 640 p. 6. Hops, N.D. Theoretical foundations of professional teacher training / N.D. Hop. - Almaty: Gylym, 1998. - 320 p.